

The Influence of Students' Perceptions and Gender Issues on Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Secondary Schools in Trans-Nzoia County, Kenya

Juliana Cherop Chirchir^{1*}, Anne Syomwene¹

¹Department of curriculum, instruction and educational media, School of education Moi University, Eldoret- Kenya

*Corresponding author's Email: julichero@gmail.com

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Abstract

Science education is an important component for economic and technological development in Kenya, In pursuit of Kenyas' Vision 2030. This paper is a report of a study that was carried out in the year 2018 on the influence of students' perceptions and gender issues on students' achievement in Chemistry in secondary schools in Trans-Nzoia County in Kenya. The study was guided by the Systems theory by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy. It employed a mixed methods approach and a descriptive survey design. The study targeted 8316 respondents that included teachers of Chemistry and form 3 students taking Chemistry subject from 33 secondary schools. Stratified sampling, simple random sampling, purposive sampling and census sampling methods were used to obtain a sample size of 28 teachers and 825 students of Chemistry. Data was collected using students' questionnaires and teachers' interview schedules. Data analysis was done by use of descriptive statistics and thematic analysis methods. The findings indicated that students' perceptions in Chemistry and gender issues had an influence achievement in the subject. 53% of students revealed that they preferred other subjects to Chemistry. Most of the students (68%) revealed that the language used in Chemistry exams was very difficult. Most of the teachers opined that students' perceptions in Chemistry influenced their performance in the subject. 64% of the students mentioned that they performed poorly in Chemistry because it doesn't favor their gender. The study recommended that students' should be sensitized on the significance of Chemistry in everyday life and in various careers. Teachers should simplify the language used in Chemistry examinations. Teachers should provide an enabling environment in the teaching of Chemistry and encourage both boys and girls to work hard in the subject. The findings of this study inform education stakeholders on the significance of students' perceptions and gender issues in academic achievement.

Key Words: Perceptions, gender issues, Chemistry, Students' achievement

INTRODUCTION

Students' academic achievement is usually an important aspect in the process of teaching and learning. Teachers would want to see the kind of progress the learners make after undergoing a certain course. The same case applies to the education stakeholders: government, parents and learners too. Academic performance is usually assessed through tests or examinations, which consists of set questions or problems that seek to determine how much an individual understands about the subject area as a result of learning experience (Aikenand, 2010).

The world is dominated by technologies, thus forcing every nation to strive to keep abreast with scientific and technological advances besides integrating it into its education system. Therefore, Science is a fundamental requirement if the world is to be transformed into a better place to live in, as it plays a key role in a country's education system. Many African countries treat the training of scientific and technological personnel as a top priority. This is due to the recognition of the fact that rapid social and economic development is not easy to achieve in the absence of qualified doctors, engineers, teachers and technicians (Aikenand, 1997).

Kenya must address herself to the quest for scientific knowledge in order to develop and sustain the necessary technologies to compete effectively in the global scene. Science education has been seen as an important component for technological development in the Kenya. Eshiwani (1983) argues that more, formal and intensive science education at secondary level is necessary in order to prepare the future scientists and technicians. The skills acquired by such people will be useful in areas such as health, agriculture and industry. Chemistry is a way of life (KNEC, 2018). It is important in the day-to-day human activities such as food processing, Agriculture, Pharmacy, Medicine and industrial processes. Despite the significance of Chemistry in daily life and in the job market, there has been poor performance in Chemistry subject in Kenya (KNEC, 2015, 2016, 2017 & 2018) as shown in Table 1. The poor performance in Chemistry has been a major concern for parents, teachers, and educators in the country. The poor performance on Chemistry by the students has been linked to such factors as their perceptions and gender issues.

Table 1: Mean Scores for Trans-Nzoia County for Chemistry

Years	2014	2015	2016	2017
Mean Score	3.361	3.197	2.003	2.107
Max Score	12.0	12.0	12.0	12.0

Source: KNEC Reports (2015, 2016, 2017 & 2018)

The objectives of secondary school Chemistry in Kenya is to (1) produce competent graduates who would apply practical skills acquired to develop their mental faculties and thus improve their society, (2) discover and understand the order of the physical environment, (3) make the learner aware of the effect of scientific knowledge in everyday life through application to the management and (4) conservation of the environment, the utilization of resources and production of goods and to inculcate in the learner a willingness to co-operate in using scientific knowledge to foster development in the society (MOE, 2019). It is important to note that following the poor results in Chemistry, these objectives have been partially achieved over the years.

Chemistry subject can greatly contribute to the achievement of Vision 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals in Kenya. Favorable achievement of students' in Chemistry can aid in the achievement of plans of economic development in Kenya by increasing science professionals in the job market. The perception of students has been found to have an impact on the how students perform in various subjects in schools Chemistry included (Kerlinger, 1983; Syomwene, Nyandusi & Yungungu, 2017; Syomwene & Kitainge, 2013). Students who have a positive perception towards a subject have been found to perform better as compared to those who have negative perception. Similarly, various studies have found out that gender issues influence students' performance in Chemistry (Jebet & Naserian, 2003; Jepkoech, 2002; Laureau, 2012). The study was an investigation on the influence of students' perceptions and gender issues on their achievement in Chemistry in secondary schools.

In Kenya, there is a nationwide concern that performance in Sciences (Chemistry included) is poor and the trend has been observed for some years. In the KNEC report of 2017, schools were asked to instill measures that would enhance students' performance in Chemistry. In Trans-Nzoia County, poor performance in Chemistry was witnessed in several years as shown in Table 1. It's imperative to investigate the factors that would be contributing to the poor performance.

It is difficult to envision a developing nation being unable to achieve technological advancement with a large manpower base ignorant or unable to handle the same technology, owing to inherent phobia to Sciences. Various studies reveal a relationship between students' perceptions and their academic achievement (Nur, 2012; Adesoji & Olatunbosun, 2012). Kerlinger (1983) states that learners' perception affect the willingness of an individual to take part in certain activities and the way in which they respond to person, objects, or situation.

This means that the learner will be ready and willing to learn and work hard in Chemistry if their perception is positive. Similarly, various studies have found out that gender issues influence students' performance in Chemistry (Jebet & Naserian, 2003; Jepkoech, 2002; Laureau, 2012). This study intended to shed light on the influence of students' perceptions and gender issues on students' achievement in Chemistry in secondary schools in Trans-Nzoia County, Kenya

The purpose of the study was to find out the influence of students' perceptions and gender issues on students' achievement in Chemistry in secondary schools in Trans-Nzoia County in Kenya.

The research objectives for the study were to investigate the influence of:

- (i) Students' perceptions to Chemistry on their achievement in the subject.
- (ii) Gender issues on students' achievement in Chemistry.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section presents the literature review on students' perceptions and gender issues and their influence in students' academic achievement. The theoretical framework for the paper has been discussed too.

Students' Perceptions and their Influence in their Academic Achievement

Bernstein, Penner, Clarke-Stewart & Roy, (2006) defines perception towards schooling denotes a positive or negative predisposition towards schooling and every activity in the school environment, which could be cognitive, emotional, or behavioral. On the other hand, Jebet and Naserian (2003) the readiness to respond to stimuli embedded is in one's willingness to learn new concepts in Chemistry. Kerlinger (1983) states that students' perception affects the willingness of an individual to take part in certain activities and the way in which they respond to person, objects, or situation. Kochhar (1992) observes that a student's readiness to learn is determined by their attitudes to the subject at hand. This means that the learner will be ready and willing to learn Chemistry if their perception of it is positive. When perceptions are positive they will not only affect what is being taught but also the effort being employed in the tackling tasks given which would enhance success in life.

According to Popham (2005), students' attitudes or interests should be enormously important to educators, because affective dispositions are powerful predictors of students' subsequent behaviour. In a related study, Erdogan, Bayram, Deniz (2008) found that there is a positive

relationship between students' attitudes towards modern learning technologies and their academic achievement. Academic achievement increases with the use of modern technologies positively. There is a strong association between individuals' attitudes towards education and their academic performance and commitment. Students who have negative attitudes towards education activities are found to exhibit challenging behaviour including anti-social and off-task behaviour (Awang, Jindal-Snape & Barber, 2013)

Interest plays great role in the field of psychology as some recent research works have found that it is closely related with personality, motivation, cognition, development, emotion, vocations, aesthetics, behavior, hobbies, reasoning, and information processing (Silvia, 2006) How an individual thinks feels and behaves is related to his/her self-esteem. To a certain extent, researchers have found that peers, parents and teachers exert some influence in the enrolment of students in Chemistry classes (Fensham, 1988)

Diana (2012) indicate that students' interests could play substantial role among students studying Chemistry. In Diana's study, she concluded that there was a positive relationship between the attitude of a student and performance in Chemistry (Diana, 2012). Similarly, a study done in Ghana by Clark (1983) found out that, in general, the attitudes of students towards Chemistry tend to decrease in the order, Biology, Chemistry, Physics and Mathematics. Eshiwani (1993) conducted a study in schools on performance of students in Chemistry subjects. He found that using integrated Chemistry environment activities improved high school students' attitudes towards the subject. The study found out that majority of the students who had a positive attitude towards Chemistry subject passed their exams as compared to those who had a negative attitude towards the subject. The study concluded that the attitude of a student had an impact on the achievement in Chemistry.

Perloff (2016). Asserted that attitude can be said to be the emotional and mental entities that propel an individual to take any action towards an object or subject .Attitude is also the way the mind is disposed of, feels, or conditioned toward an individual or objects Khan and Ali (2016).According to Jegede (1995) in a study conducted in Uganda, it was found that students' had their attitudes enhanced after exposing them to self-learning strategy when it comes to Chemistry. Studies have also been conducted in Kenya in regard to students' performance in Chemistry subjects. According to study conducted by Jepkoech (2002) in Nakuru county, it was found that majority of the students passed their Chemistry subject due to positive attitudes. The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between

attitude and good performance in Chemistry subject. A similar study was also conducted in Kericho district by Jebet and Naserian (2003) that focused on factors that influence student performance in Chemistry subject within secondary schools in Kericho. From the study, 88% of the students mentioned that learner perception was a major factor in the performance of the students' in Chemistry. Students' perceptions are thus a great determinant in their academic achievement. Their perceptions determine the passion, interest and effort they put in regard to various subjects and activities in education.

Students' gender and its influence on academic achievement

Gender refers to the state of being male or female. On the other hand gender issues are considered as being socially constructed roles, behaviour, activities, and attributes that a given society considers appropriate for men and women. Gender issues have been highly linked to students' performance in Sciences Chemistry included. There are various policies in Kenya that are related to gender, and these include having lower entry points for girls than boys when joining universities (Aduda, 2009). Gender refers to socially constructed differences between male and female.

Normally girls are treated differently from boys from an early age by their parents. Boys are encouraged by parents to be more adventurous and forceful and are more likely to have hobbies and interests dealing with electrical, mechanical devices and chemicals. They may be asked to help their fathers in doing technical tasks in the house and garden and to use tools such as electric drills, saws and hammers. Girls, by contrast, are more likely to be asked to play with soft toys or to help their mothers with housework and not to involve themselves in dangerous activities which could hurt them. Such interests, hobbies and behaviour could be linked to boys' preference for science subjects such as Chemistry. Many experiments in Chemistry involve equipment and tools which are unfamiliar to girls. Boys, therefore, get a better chance to process scientific knowledge in schools (Aduda, 2009).

Within the school environment, gender identities are constructed through informal processes such as peer culture. Girls are expected to adopt roles, behaviour and identities which allow inclusion and integration with their peers. These issues impact on the girls' confidence, self-esteem and their engagement in academic subjects (Bude, 1982). How an individual thinks, feels and behaves is related to his/her self-esteem. To a certain extent, researchers have found that peers, parents and teachers exert some influence in the enrolment of students in Chemistry classes (Fenshman, 1988).

Girls tend to be more influenced by their friends than are boys, particularly in single-sex schools (Eshiwani, 1993). It has been suggested by researchers that peer culture tends to be an important factor in determining the behaviour and personality of young people (Jepkoech, 2002). Interaction with peers can be particularly influential in the choice of Chemistry subject. As noted by Previc (2011) girls are generally more inclined to study Biology and less likely to choose Chemistry.

According to Sparks-Wallace (2007) males' comparative advantage when it comes to academic performance in time past reinforced the notion of males' intellectual superiority over females and often disregarded the structural impediments and stereotypes that inhibited females' academic abilities, especially in the sciences. Recent studies in the developed world have shown a reversal in academic performance between males and females, with females outperforming males in almost all disciplines at various levels of the educational ladder

Recent studies in developing countries have also shown marked improvement in female academic performance Ullah and Ullah (2019), and this is against the backdrop of persistent challenges with access to education, and under-representation in STEM programmes

In most parts of Africa, male folks are viewed as possessing superior characteristics in most thus, it is widely believed that male endeavours (Tambaya, Sabitu, and Matazu 2016)

,students perform better in science-based subjects as compared to their female counter-parts This fact also stems from the recurring gender difference in the performance of secondary school students in science subjects particularly, in chemistry

Fenshman (1988) study found out that males performed significantly better on Chemistry achievement tests compared to girls. According to a study conducted by Jegede (1995) it was found that many girls in secondary schools in Nigeria were performing poorly in sciences which included Chemistry. The study was an investigation on how gender affects the performance of a student towards Chemistry. A similar study was conducted by Eshiwani (1986) in Egypt that aimed at identifying factors that influence students' performance in Chemistry among high school students. From the findings, 88% of the teachers identified gender as one of the factors that affected students' performance.

A study on girls and education in Uganda by Laureau (2012) on influence of gender on the performance of the students in Chemistry found out that gender was affecting students' performance in Chemistry. Same study was also carried among schools in Rwanda. The study aimed to find out how gender affects the performance of students in Chemistry. The study targeted 500 teachers of Chemistry within the selected schools. From

the findings, 90% of teachers revealed that gender was affecting students' performance in Chemistry.

In Kenya, a study was conducted by Jebet and Naserian, (2003) in Nyamira. It aimed to find out if there was a relationship between gender and performance in Chemistry. The study performed a regression analysis that found out there was a significant relationship between gender of the students and their performance in Chemistry. A study was also conducted in Bomet county by Jepkoech (2002) in which 77% of the teachers responded that gender had a great influence on how students performed in Chemistry.

Theoretical Framework

The study was based on the Systems theory by Ludwid von Bertalanffy(1968; Sherry and Urry 2003). The argument of this theory is that a system consists of various components or sub-systems that must function in harmony for the system to work. If a subsystem fails, the whole system is in jeopardy. As in the systems theory, students' achievement can be taken as a system. Students' achievement in Chemistry can be influenced by many factors such as students' perceptions in the subject and gender issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study utilized a mixed methods approach and a descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Trans-Nzoia County. The study targeted 8316 respondents for the study that included teachers of Chemistry and form 3 students taking Chemistry subject from 33 secondary schools. Stratified sampling, simple random sampling, purposive sampling and census sampling methods were used to obtain a sample size of 28 teachers and 825 students of Chemistry. Data was collected using students' questionnaires and teachers' interview schedules.

The validity of the research instruments was ascertained through expert opinion from the lecturers and colleagues. The researcher derived the items in the research instruments from the research objectives for validity reasons. In addition, the researcher conducted a pilot study at Kapsoya secondary in Uasin Gishu County to ascertain the validity of the research instruments. The feedback obtained was used to revise and review the research instruments.

The reliability of the instruments was tested using the Cronbach alpha test. The findings of the reliability revealed as strength of 0.87 which was found appropriate. To ensure that the study complied with the ethical issues pertaining research undertaking, a permission to

conduct the research was sought from the respective authorities. Data analysis was done by use of descriptive statistics and thematic analysis methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first research objective was to find out the influence of students' perceptions to Chemistry on their achievement in the subject. The findings indicated that half of the students (50%) were passionate about Chemistry as they found it interesting. However, 40% of students revealed that they preferred other subjects to Chemistry. Most of the students (68%) revealed that language used in Chemistry exams was very difficult making exam questions challenging and confusing. Most of the teachers opined that students' perceptions in Chemistry greatly influenced their performance in the subject.

The findings concur with/ that of Diana (2012) that found out that the language used in examinations can affect students' perceptions in a subject. Students' positive perceptions to Chemistry correlate highly with their Chemistry achievement. The study further indicated that there is a positive relationship between the perceptions of a student and performance in Chemistry.

The second research objective was to find out the influence of gender issues on students' achievement in Chemistry. From the findings, 60% of the students indicated that gender played a role in their achievement in Chemistry. The findings of the study indicate that 66% of the students felt that boys do well in Chemistry compared to girls. Also, 64% of the students mentioned that they perform poorly in Chemistry because it doesn't favor their gender.

The teachers opined that gender issues rarely affected students' performance in Chemistry and where it happened it was important to create of an enabling environment such as availability of resources and proper teaching techniques.

The findings of the study concur with the findings of the study that was conducted by Fenshman (1988) and Jepkoech (2002) that found out that gender issues played a crucial role in students' performance in Chemistry.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that students' perceptions in Chemistry and gender issues had an influence in their achievement in the subject. It recommended that students' should be sensitized on the significance of Chemistry in everyday life and in various careers. Teachers

should simplify the language used in Chemistry examinations. Teachers should provide an enabling environment in the teaching of Chemistry and encourage both boys and girls to work hard in the subject.

BIO DATA

Juliana Cherop Chirchir is a holder of a M.ED degree in Curriculum Studies from Moi University. She's currently pursuing a PhD in Curriculum Studies from the same institution. In addition, Juliana is a seasoned teacher of Chemistry in a secondary school in Trans-Nzoia County.

Anne Syomwene is an Associate Professor in Curriculum Studies in Moi University. She's a holder of a PhD and M.ED degree in Curriculum Studies from Moi University. She has authored many books and many papers in refereed journals. She has a wide experience in thesis supervision and examination.

REFERENCES

- Adesoji, F. A., & Olatunbosun, S. M. (2008). Student, teacher and school environment factors as determinants of achievement in senior secondary school Chemistry in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of international social research, 1*(2).
- Aduda, D. (2009). *Top marks for Alliance*. Daily Nation; Nation Media Nation Group: Nairobi.
- Aikenand, G. (2010). *Chemistry education: Border crossing into the sub culture*. Lagos: Lagos publishers.
- Aikenland, G. S. (1997). *Curriculum chemistry education: Towards a first nations cross cultural Chemistry and technology*. New York: Sage Publishers
- Bertalanffy, L. V. (2003). *General systems theory: Foundations, development, applications*. New York: George Brazillier.
- Bude, U. (1982). *Curriculum development in Africa*. Unpublished.
- Clark, R. (1983). *Family life and school achievement: Why poor black children succeed of fail*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Diana, R. (2012). "Rearing competent children." In *child development today and tomorrow*. Kigali: Views publishers
- Eshiwani, G. S. (1986). *Chemistry, Mathematics and Technology education*. Nairobi: The Kenya Bureau of Educational Research.

- Eshiwani, G. S. (1993). *Factors influencing performance among primary and secondary school pupils in Western province of Kenya*. Nairobi: The Kenya Bureau of Educational Research.
- Fenshman, P. (Ed) (1988). *Development and dilemmas in Chemistry education*. Bangladesh: Falmer Press publishers
- Jebet, M. & Naserian, S. (2003). *Poor performance in Chemistry subject threatens technologies advancement, Kenya Times*. Nairobi: Kenya Times Media Publishers.
- Jegede, O. J. (1995). *Studies in Chemistry education: Collateral learning and eco-cultural*. Nairobi: Kenya Times Media Publishers.
- Jepkoech, S. (2002). *Survey of factors that influence the performance of student in economics in KCSE: a case study of selected schools in Rift Valley province*: Nairobi: Kenya
- Kerlinger, F. N. (1983). *Foundations of behaviour research*. Holt: Rheinhert and Winston publishers
- Lareau, A. (2012). *Home advantage: Social class and parental intervention in elementary education*. New York: Falmer Press.
- Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) (2015). *KCSE Newsletter*. Nairobi: KNEC
- Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) (2016). *KCSE Newsletter*. Nairobi: KNEC
- Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) (2017). *KCSE Newsletter*. Nairobi: KNEC
- Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) (2018). *KCSE Newsletter*. Nairobi: KNEC
- Kochhar, S. K. (1992). *Methods and techniques of teaching*. New Delhi: Sterling publishers limited
- Ministry of Education (MOE) (2019). *Kenya secondary school syllabus*. Nairobi: MOE
- Nur, M. A. (2010). Factors that influence secondary school students' performance in Mathematics in Banadir Region, Somalia. *Unpublished Master's thesis, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya*.
- Syomwene, A., Nyandusi, C. & Yungungu, A. (Eds.). (2017). *Core Principles in Curriculum*. Eldoret: Utafiti Foundation.
- Syomwene, A., & Kitainge, K. M., (December, 2013). Post Graduates Students Perception on the significance on a course on gender and education and its applicability in the teaching profession. *Journal of Gender practices and challenges*. Eldoret: Moi University press (pp 87-98)
- Previc, F. H. (2011). *A general theory concerning the prenatal origins of cerebral Lateralization in humans*. Illinois: Educational Foundation press.